

Utility of Hydrazidoyl Chlorides : Synthesis of New Pyrazoles, Pyrazolo[3,4-*d*]pyridazines, Pyrazolo[4,5-*b*]pyridines and Pyrazolo[4,5-*d*]pyrimidine Derivatives

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Hydrazidoyl chlorides (1) were reacted with a variety of active methylene compounds and arylidenemalononitriles in basic medium, to produce polyfunctionally substituted pyrazole derivatives (2–6 and 10). The pyrazoles (2, 3, 6 and 10) were converted into the corresponding pyrazolo[3,4-*d*]pyridazine derivatives (7–9 and 14), respectively. The aminopyrazole derivative (10) underwent dipolar cycloaddition with acetylisothiocyanate, acrylonitrile and arylidenemalononitrile to produce pyrazolo[4,5-*d*]pyrimidine (15) and pyrazolo[4,5-*b*]pyridines (16, 17) respectively. Their structures were established on the basis of elemental analyses and spectral data.

Hydrazidoyl chlorides being reactive intermediates have received considerable attention¹ in the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds. In continuation to our program of utilising hydrazidoyl halides in the development of new procedures for the synthesis of azoles and fused azoles², which have activities, we report herein the results of our investigation on the reaction of hydrazidoyl chlorides (1) with the carbanions of β -keto esters and β -diketones. The hydrazidoyl chlorides (1) were reacted with ethyl benzoylacetate, aceto-*N*-acetyl-*p*-anisidine, aceto-*N*-acetyl-*p*-chloroaniline and aceto-*N*-acetylmorpholine in ethanol solution to produce the corresponding pyrazoles (2–5). Also, the hydrazidoyl chlorides (1) were reacted with arylidenemalononitrile to produce the pyrazole derivatives (6). Structure of 6 was confirmed on the basis of chemical evidence derived from the fact that it reacted with hydrazine hydrate to produce pyrazolo[3,4-*d*]pyridazine (9). Furthermore, pyrazolo[3,4-*d*]pyridazines (7 and 8) were obtained by the reaction of the pyrazoles (2 and 3) with hydrazine hydrate, respectively (Scheme 1).

The reaction of hydrazidoyl halide with activated nitriles has been reported³. In the present investigation, the reaction of 1 with malononitrile in sodium ethoxide led to the formation of the new aminopyrazole derivatives (10). The latter compounds were reacted with acetyl chloride and benzenesulphonyl chloride in dry pyridine to give the corresponding *N*-substituted pyrazole derivatives (11 and 12, respectively). Also, compound 10 was reacted with *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde to produce the Schiff's base 13 in ethanol-piperidine solution. The structure of 10 was established chemically by its reaction with hydrazine hydrate to give the corresponding pyrazolo[3,4-*d*]pyridazine (14) as described previously.

X = a:	P-Cl		X	Y
b:	P-CH ₃			
Ar:		(4a _i)	Cl	OCH ₃
		(4a _{ii})	Cl	Cl
		(4b _i)	CH ₃	OCH ₃
		(4b _{ii})	CH ₃	Cl

Scheme 1

The reaction of alkyl isothiocyanate with aminoazoles has been reported⁴. In the present investigation the reaction of 10 with acetyl isothiocyanate was found to give directly the corresponding pyrazolo[4,5-*d*]pyrimidinethione (15) and not the expected acyclic thiourea derivatives as reported in other cases⁴. Finally, the aminopyrazole (10) was reacted with ethylenic compounds such as acrylonitrile and arlyidenemalononitrile in dry pyridine, to produce the corresponding pyrazolo[4,5-*b*]pyridine derivatives (16 and 17, respectively). Presumably, the formation of 17 starts by Michael addition followed by cyclisation and by loss of HCN (Scheme 2). Structures of all the compounds were established on the basis of elemental analyses and spectral data (Table 1).

Scheme 2

Gemini (200 MHz) spectrometer. Analytical data of the compounds (Table 1) were obtained from the Microanalytical Center at Cairo University.

TABLE 1—SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	ν_{max} cm ⁻¹	δ
2a	116	1 720 (CO ester), 1 670 (CO)	1.3 (3H, t, CH ₃), 2.6 (3H, s, CH ₃ CO), 4.2 (2H, q, CH ₂), 7.4–8.2 (9H, m, ArH)
2b	112	—	—
3a	150	1 672, 1 668 (two CO)	2.5–2.6 (6H, 2s, 2 × CH ₃ CO), 7.3–8.2 (9H, m, ArH)
3b	98	—	—
4a	101	1 685, 1 665 (two CO)	2.5 (3H s, CH ₃ -pyrazole), 2.7 (3H, s, CH ₃ CO) 7.2–7.8 (9H, m, ArH), 10.9 (1H, s, NH)
4ai	137	—	—
4bi	108	—	—
4bi	135	—	—
5b	123	1 680, 1 665 (two CO)	—
6a	132	2 210 (CN), 1 668 (two CO)	2.6 (3H, s, CH ₃ CO), 3.7 (3H, s, CH ₃ CO) 7.4–7.6 (8H, m, ArH)
6b	145	—	—
7a	205	3 300 (NH), 1 680 (CO)	2.8 (3H, s, CH ₃ -pyridazine), 7.4–8.2 (9H, m, ArH), 11.9 (1H, s, NH)
7b	253	—	—
8a	225	1 605 (C=N)	2.7–2.8 (6H, 2s, 2 × CH ₃ -pyridazine), 7.4–7.8 (9H, m, ArH)
9a	218	3 200 (NH ₂)	—
10a	187	3 200 (NH ₂), 2 210 (CN), 1 665 (CO)	2.6 (3H, s, CH ₃ CO), 7.0 (2H, s, NH ₂), 7.6–8.0 (4H, m, ArH)
10b	206	—	—
11a	191	3 100 (NH), 2 210 (CN), 1 670, 1 665 (two CO)	2.5–2.7 (6H, 2s, 2 × CH ₃ CO), 7.4–7.8 (4H, m, ArH), 10.4 (1H, s, NH)
11b	180	—	—
12a	173	3 300 (NH), 2 210 (CN), 1 665 (CO)	2.6 (3H, s, CH ₃ CO), 7.3–8.4 (9H, m, ArH), 10.9 (1H, s, NH)
13a	178	2 210 (CN), 1 665 (CO)	—
14a	240	3 300–3 000 (NH ₂)	2.0 (3H, s, CH ₃ -pyridazine), 6.6–6.7 (4H, 2s, NH ₂), 7.6 (4H, s, ArH)
15b	160	3 100 (NH), 1 680, 1 665 (two CO)	—
16b	154	3 200–3 000 (NH ₂), 2 220 (CN), 1 665 (CO)	—
17b	145	3 300–3 000 (NH ₂), 2 210 (CN), 1 665 (CO)	—

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and Cl (wherever applicable) analyses; ¹³C nmr (CDCl₃) for 10a : δ 25 (CH₃), 114 (2-*m*-carbons), 130 (2-*p*-carbons), 142 (CO) and 181 ppm (CN).

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP-1100 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra on a Varian

Preparation of 2–5 and 10: To an ethanolic sodium ethoxide solution (prepared from 0.01 mol

sodium metal and 30 ml ethanol) was added each of ethyl benzoylacetate, benzoylacetone, aceto-*N*-acetyl-*p*-anisidine, aceto-*n*-acetyl-*p*-chloroaniline, aceto-*N*-acetylmorpholine and malononitrile (0.01 ml). After stirring the resulting solution for 3 min at room temperature, the appropriate hydrazidoyl chloride (1a, b ; 0.01 mol) was added to it and stirring continued for 2 h. The reaction mixture was then left overnight at room temperature, poured over ice-water and acidified with few drops of dilute HCl. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to give 2, 3, 4, 5 and 10, respectively (72–90%).

Reaction of 1 with arylidenemalononitrile: To a suspension of 1 (0.01 mol) in dry benzene (10 ml) containing a few drops of triethylamine, α -cyano-cinnamionitrile (0.01 mol) was added, and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 h. The solvent was then distilled off and the product was acidified with dilute HCl. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to give 6 (60–68%).

Reaction of hydrazine hydrate with 2, 3, 6 and 10: To a suspension of each of 2, 3, 6 and 10 (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 ml), hydrazine hydrate (0.02 mol) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 h, then poured over ice-cold dilute HCl and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to give 7, 8, 9 and 14, respectively (71–80%).

Reaction of 10 with acetyl chloride and benzenesulphonyl chloride: To a suspension of 10 (0.01 mol) in dry pyridine (20 ml), acetyl chloride or benzenesulphonyl chloride (0.01 mol) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 h, then poured over cold concentrated HCl and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to give 11 or 12 (72–88%).

Reaction of 10 with p-chlorobenzaldehyde: A mixture of 10 (0.01 mol) and *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde (0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) containing a few drops of piperidine was refluxed for 2 h. The solvent

was then evaporated to half of its volume, cooled and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to give 13 (75%).

Reaction of 10 with acetylthiocyanate, acrylonitrile and α -cyanocinnamionitrile: To a suspension of 10 (0.01 mol) in dry pyridine (20 ml), acetylthiocyanate, acrylonitrile or α -cyanocinnamionitrile (0.01 mol) was added, and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 5 h. It was then poured over ice-cold concentrated HCl and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to yield 15, 16 and 17, respectively (52–66%).

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